

Recognition of Human activity using Machine Learning Models

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Abstract:

Recently, smartphones have emerged as a popular research topic and are becoming increasingly important in identifying human behavior. Detailed synopsis of numerous scholarly publications on this study discusses the recognition of human action. Artificial Intelligence (AI) models are created to identify human activities from the UCI online repository. We have utilized a range of machine classification approaches, including Random Forest, kNN, Neural Network, Logistic Regression, Stochastic Gradient Descent, and Naïve Bayes, to analyze the human behavior in the multivariate data. In addition to creating AI models, the feature selection procedure reduces the dataset's dimension. For every model, a confusion matrix was created and precision and recall values were computed. The results of the experiment showed that, despite requiring more memory and processing power, Random Forest perform better at recognizing human activity than other classifiers like Logistic regression and Gradient Boosting.

Keywords: Logistic Regression, Gradient Boosting, Random Forest.

Introduction

Numerous applications with human-centered monitoring have been developed to identify, detect, and categorize human behavior, and several methods have been offered by researchers. One of the key pieces of technology for tracking a person's dynamism is human activity detection, which machine learning techniques can help achieve. The simpler and quicker threshold-based approach is frequently used to identify human activities. However, a dependable outcome will be calculated by machine algorithm. A multitude of sensors have been utilized to monitor the dynamic features of human behavior. The purpose of this research is to evaluate several machine learning classification techniques. Our study is driven by the need to apply deep learning techniques to real-world datasets in demand to investigate their correctness and derive useful findings.

A camera module that records dataset used as an input by the recognition system can be recycled to implement the social movement prediction paradigm. Following feature extraction, movement prediction is carried out by generating distinct frames of such input data. When such behavior is recognized as either normal or suspicious, an instant alert is issued to the relevant authorities.

Literature Review

Anguita et al. (2012) provided evidence of how human activities are identified by utilizing disparate sensors to provide adjustments to exogenous registering assets. Once these sensors are connected to the subject's body, they enable continuous monitoring of multiple physiological indicators. He has created a framework that makes use of an inertial navigation system to identify physical human activities. Given the limited processing capacity and battery life of mobile cell phones, an equipment friendly methodology is suggested for multiclass classification. Every command to reduce computing costs, this method modifies the basic deep learning algorithms and attempts fixed-point number juggling. An analysis using the standard SVM shows a significant

improvement in terms of computing costs while maintaining comparable precision, which can contribute to the enhancement of increasingly maintainable frameworks for Aml.[1]

Shahroudy et al. (2016) looked at more recent approaches for top-to-bottom based human movement analysis. They achieved remarkable results and showed that 3D representation is a feasible option for organizing activity classes. Currently available depth-based and RGB+D-based activity recognition benchmarks have a number of limitations, such as the lack of prep tests, distinct class names, camera angles, and a variety of subjects. This study presents a large-scale raw data for motion movement prediction, comprising 4 million edges and 56,000 video tests collected from 40 specific participants. It includes sixty individual motion class, such as communal, daily, and wellness-focused activities. Additionally, a different repeated neural system structure is suggested in order to show how the highlights of each body part are connected over the long term and to utilize this information for accurate activity categorization. Lastly, it was shown how implementing profound learning strategies—which include cross-subject and cross-assessment criteria for the selected dataset—benefits cutting edge research. [2]

According to Oyelade et al. (2010), a fundamental problem for the academic network of higher education is capable to track the progress of understudies' scholarly execution. A framework for decomposing experiments understudy based on group assessment and using standard, quantifiable computations to master the knowledge about their scores as suggested by the execution's dimension is presented. Cluster analysis and conventional statistical techniques are implemented and considered student dataset including the student score of a specific semester in order to evaluate the academic result of the students. The input for the selected random samples is the counting of clusters to be obtained. Once the arithmetic mean of every cluster has been determined, the procedure is carried out again until the raw data remain unchanged. For the selected semester, which offers nine courses, the performance is assessed using a deterministic model, and a fuzzy classifiers are used to forecast their academic achievement. [3]

Self-sorting guide are useful tool for representing multidimensional numerical data, according to Vesanto et al. (1999). This paper presents an evaluation and ranking of both contemporary and traditional methods for perceiving SOM. The motive of this is to consider the kind of information that may be gleaned from different introductions and the optimal way to apply the SOM to exploratory information perception. Maximum approaches that are shown can also relative to the more general case of creating a vector quantization first and a vector projection second [4].

An proposal for programmed focus on highlights within a volumetric informative index was provided by Viola et al. (2010). The customer selects a focal point, or object of passion, from a variation of pre-described highlights. The most expressive perspective on this component is inherently calculated with the help of architecture put out here. A unique data theoretic system that relies on the shared data measure assesses a trademark standpoint. By shifting the focus from one

element to the next, perspectives can be changed with ease. Differences in the spreading of significance among the volume's highlights impose constraints on this instrument. The element in core interest is given the most remarkable significance. By establishing perspective, the centering element guides visual accentuation by designating a more pronounced representation. For example, centering allows for the reasonable view of highlights that are frequently obscured by various portions of the volume by consolidating remove views.[5]

According to Jiang et al. (2009), developing an ideal Bayesian system classifier is an NP-difficult problem; hence, scientists have given learning-improved innocent Bayes maximum thought. This study presents updated computations and suggests a hidden innocent Bayes (HNB). Each feature in HNB has a veiled parent that unites the properties of all other properties. The 36 UCI informational collections that Weka selected are used to test the characterization exactness of HNB. It is then compared to gullible Bayes (NB), specific bayes classifier innocent Bayes tree, tree-expanded guileless Bayes, and the middle value of one-reliance estimators (AODE). [6]

Vincenzi et al. (2011) introduced a demonstrative framework that combines artificial intelligence techniques with geographic information systems to support the management of Manila shellfish, a crucial aquaculture species (*Rudi tapes philippinarum*). They used the Venice Tidal Pond in Italy, which is the main location in Europe where *R. Phillipinarum* was first discovered and explain efficacy of this method. An independent experiment accepted the RF demonstration after it was adjusted using a broad deep learning model. The model often predicted high site-explicit yields, and the analysis of small effect indicators showed a good degree of agreement between the reactions that were shown and easily available natural learning for *R. philippinarum*. [7]

The approach for identifying person facial emotions from recorded films was proposed by Jie Hu et al. (2013). Bounding box detection from a sequence of photos rendered in three layers is the effort, and the selected Weizmann dataset includes nine distinct human behaviors from ten different persons. The constructed model includes both the spatial and temporal components to represent the typical features. [8]

(2011) Aggarwal et al. Sequential techniques and space-time volume approaches to identify the activities from the input photos were discussed.[9]

The mainstream of these applications call for a robot to recognize abnormal state workouts, which are composed of different simple (or complex) human actions. An outline of several best-in-class research publications on human action acknowledgment may be found in this article. A scientific classification based on technique is chosen, and it examines the advantages and shortcomings of each methodology. Eneaer al. (2016) talked about calculated characteristics from skeleton joints, human computer interface, and low-cost RGB-D sensor use in surveillance. A histogram was created using the skeleton features, which were identified by different key poses. When associated to the currently available arrangements, the existing approaches' focus on minor AI estimates didn't produce the greatest results. [10]

Ms. S. Robini et al. (2019) identified human movements using a deep learning technique. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that Recurrent ANN with Long Short Term Memory

(RNNLSTM) offers superior accuracy with a lower mean absolute percentage error. As a result, they proposed using RNNLSTM to lessen human fatalities by identifying human activity in the real world. [12]

In smart environments, person activity prediction is still in its infancy as a topic of study. After preprocessing and segmentation processes, characteristics can be extracted from the raw sensor data to determine the presentation of person actions. Activity recognition relies heavily on feature selection, therefore before sending the data to the classifier, the right features must be selected and, if needed, dimensionality reductions done. ([13], [14], [15]).

Implementation

A. Data Collection

In computer science, deep techniques is the newest big thing. The aim of this research is to apply artificial techniques to actual data sets in respect examine their accuracy and derive useful conclusions. In this job, we create artificial intelligence (AI) models using the "Human Activity Recognition Using Smartphones Data Set" from the online repository of the University of California, Irvine. This informational index was created using the diaries of thirty human volunteers who were captured using cell phones with inertial sensor attached. This information is used as teaching material in several AI courses. There are several arrangements involved. There are 561 segments and 10,299 lines in the informational collection. Thirty participants between the ages of eighteen and fifty participated in the examination. Each person used a cell phone on their stomach while engaging in physical activities such as walking, walking upstairs, walking downstairs, sitting, standing, and lying down. With the use of its implanted accelerometer and gyator, we were able to record three hub rakish speeds and three pivotal straight ascending speeds at a constant 50Hz. Video recordings of the analyses have been made in order to identify the physical data.

Clamor channels were used to preprocess the sensor signals (whirligig and accelerometer), which were then evaluated in fixed-width sliding windows lasting 2.56 seconds.

The sensor quickening signal—which consists of both body movement and gravitational components—was separated into body acceleration and gravity using a Butterworth low-pass channel. Since it is acknowledged that the gravitational power only has low recurrence components, a channel with a 0.3 Hz cutoff recurrence was used. A vector of highlights from each window was obtained by factoring in the time and recurrence area. Orange Tool was utilized to develop classification algorithms on multivariate data. Additionally, a Python neural network with dropouts has been created, yielding improved results. To complete the intended work, Python imports the libraries TensorFlow, Keras, and NumPy.

B. Research Methodology

Given that the data presents a multivariate classification challenge, both supervised and unsupervised learning algorithms have been employed. The Neural Network implementation in Python with dropouts was done using the Orange Tool, and the outcome was superior. The Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Stochastic Gradient Descent, and Decision tree modules all received the dataset. A confusion matrix was created for each model based on the calculations of their precision and recall values. Fig. 1 displays the suggested system's architecture diagram.

Figure 1: Research Methodology Architecture Diagram

The machine learning algorithm random forest is effective for jobs involving both regression and classification. Numerous choice trees are formed by arbitrary forests. From the preparation data, a bootstrap test is used to generate each tree. Decide how many desirable tree can be added to the woods and various traits will be boldly shown for contributed at each hub. This number is equal to the square base of the number of traits in the data if the last isn't specified (option Number of Properties... left unchecked). The idea put up by Unique Breiman is to grow the trees without pre-pruning; however, since pre-pruning is faster and more effective, the client can determine the depth at which the trees will be developed.

A loss function was added to the normal logistic regression model, and the regularization type (L1 or L2) and cost strength were selected. In comparison to Naïve Bayes, it produces better results while analyzing human activities. In comparison to various deep learning approaches, it produced better accuracy and is among the best-performing models. It can lower the noise and manage any nonlinear effects.

The stochastic gradient descent widget minimizes a selected loss function. To avoid overfitting, choose the method settings aimed at the reversion loss function, classification loss function, and norms. When the learning parameters are finally fixed, the learning rate determines the outcome. The starting learning rate is set at 0.0100, and count the iterations—or runs through the training data—is fixed at 1000.

C. Results and Discussion (Implement Different AI Classifier algorithms):

i. Logistic Regression

```
# Importing necessary Libraries

from sklearn import linear_model
from sklearn import metrics

from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV

# Creating a List Labels to be added to plots

labels=['Laying', 'Sitting', 'Standing', 'Walking', 'Walking_Downstairs', 'Walking_Upstairs']

# Let's define the parameters to be tuned

parameters = {'C':[20, 25, 30, 35, 40], 'penalty':['l1', 'l2']}

# Let's initiate the model

log_reg = linear_model.LogisticRegression()
log_reg_grid = GridSearchCV(log_reg, param_grid=parameters, verbose=1, n_jobs=-1)
log_reg_grid_results = perform_model(log_reg_grid, X_train, y_train, X_test, y_test, class_labels=labels)

# Printing the best attributes of the model

print_grid_search_attributes(log_reg_grid_results['model'])
```

Training_time(HH:MM:SS.ms) - 0:00:03.267407

testing time(HH:MM:SS.ms) - 0:00:00.002174

Accuracy:

0.9613165931455717

Confusion Matrix:

Classification Report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
1	0.97	0.99	0.98	496
2	0.97	0.96	0.97	471
3	1.00	0.98	0.99	420
4	0.94	0.87	0.91	491
5	0.89	0.96	0.93	532
6	1.00	1.00	1.00	537
micro avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	2947
macro avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	2947
weighted avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	2947

Best Estimator:

```
LogisticRegression(C=30, class_weight=None, dual=False, fit_intercept=True,
intercept_scaling=1, max_iter=100, multi_class='warn',
n_jobs=None, penalty='l1', random_state=None, solver='warn',
tol=0.0001, verbose=0, warm_start=False)
```

Best parameters:

```
{'C': 30, 'penalty': 'l1'}
```

Number of CrossValidation sets:

```
3
```

Best Score:

```
0.9846300326441785
```

ii. Random Forest Classifier

```
# Importing Libraries
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier

# Let's define the parameters to be tuned
parameters = {'n_estimators': np.arange(10,201,20), 'max_depth':np.arange(4,15,2)}

# Let's initiate the model
rfc = RandomForestClassifier()
rfc_grid = GridSearchCV(rfc, param_grid=parameters, n_jobs=-1)
rfc_grid_results = perform_model(rfc_grid, X_train, y_train, X_test, y_test, class_labels=labels)

# Printing the best attributes of the model
print_grid_search_attributes(rfc_grid_results['model'])
```

Training_time(HH:MM:SS.ms) - 0:00:21.379325

testing time(HH:MM:SS.ms) - 0:00:00.034036

Accuracy:

0.9619952494061758

Confusion Matrix:

Classification Report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
1	0.97	0.99	0.98	496
2	0.98	0.97	0.98	471
3	1.00	0.98	0.99	420
4	0.96	0.86	0.91	491
5	0.88	0.97	0.92	532
6	1.00	1.00	1.00	537
micro avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	2947
macro avg	0.97	0.96	0.96	2947
weighted avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	2947

Best Estimator:

```
RandomForestClassifier(bootstrap=True, class_weight=None, criterion='gini',
max_depth=6, max_features='auto', max_leaf_nodes=None,
min_impurity_decrease=0.0, min_impurity_split=None,
min_samples_leaf=1, min_samples_split=2,
min_weight_fraction_leaf=0.0, n_estimators=110, n_jobs=None,
oob_score=False, random_state=None, verbose=0,
warm_start=False)
```

Best parameters:

```
{'max_depth': 6, 'n_estimators': 110}
```

Number of CrossValidation sets:

```
3
```

Best Score:

```
0.9857181719260065
```

iii. Gradient Boosted Classifier

```
# Importing Libraries
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingClassifier

# Let's define the parameters to be tuned
parameters = {'n_estimators': np.arange(120,150,10), 'max_depth':np.arange(3,7,1)}

# Let's initiate the model
gbdt = GradientBoostingClassifier()
gbdt_grid = GridSearchCV(gbdt, param_grid=parameters, n_jobs=-1)
gbdt_grid_results = perform_model(gbdt_grid, X_train, y_train, X_test, y_test, class_labels=labels)

# Printing the best attributes of the model
print_grid_search_attributes(gbdt_grid_results['model'])
```

Training_time(HH:MM:SS.ms) - 0:00:26.123057

testing time(HH:MM:SS.ms) - 0:00:00.033001

Accuracy:

0.9541907024092298

Confusion Matrix:

Classification Report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
1	0.99	0.99	0.99	496
2	0.98	0.97	0.98	471
3	1.00	0.92	0.96	420
4	0.91	0.88	0.89	491
5	0.87	0.96	0.91	532
6	1.00	1.00	1.00	537
micro avg	0.95	0.95	0.95	2947
macro avg	0.96	0.95	0.95	2947
weighted avg	0.96	0.95	0.95	2947

Best Estimator:

```
GradientBoostingClassifier(criterion='friedman_mse', init=None,
learning_rate=0.1, loss='deviance', max_depth=5,
max_features=None, max_leaf_nodes=None,
min_impurity_decrease=0.0, min_impurity_split=None,
min_samples_leaf=1, min_samples_split=2,
min_weight_fraction_leaf=0.0, n_estimators=140,
n_iter_no_change=None, presort='auto', random_state=None,
subsample=1.0, tol=0.0001, validation_fraction=0.1,
verbose=0, warm_start=False)
```

Best parameters:

```
{'max_depth': 5, 'n_estimators': 140}
```

Number of CrossValidation sets:

```
3
```

Best Score:

```
0.9831338411316648
```

Comparison of all Implemented AI Classifiers:

Model	Accuracy	Best Score	Error
Logistic Regression	96.13%	98.46%	3.868%
Random Forest	96.2%	98.57%	3.8%
Gradient Boosting	95.42%	98.31%	4.581%

Conclusion

In the expanding sector, human activity analysis is a prominent activity, and we have used many deep learning techniques. A comparative analysis was conducted between the several techniques that were utilized, including Random forest, Logistic regression and Gradient Boosting Machine learning classifiers. In these, outcomes of Random Forest is good, whereas the Gradient Boosting result was not up to the mark. We will have to sequence the classifiers each time new data is received because real-time data cannot be implemented to sequent it.

These findings could be implemented further to create smart watches and other similar gadgets that monitor a user's movements and provide them a daily activity report. They can similarly be recycled to keep an eye on the elderly, prisoners, or anybody else who need round-the-clock supervision.

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